

“Laparoscopic Appendectomy in Comparison With Open Appendectomy”: A General Overview

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Abstract: Surgical removal of the appendix is most frequent practice done in surgery. Unfortunately, most reliable procedure is still debatable. Both laparoscopic (LA) and open (OA) procedures are still in practice for surgical removal of appendix. Laparoscopic procedure is no doubt the gold standard for cholecystectomy, but laparoscopic approach is not widely used for surgical removal of appendix. Difficult handling, cost expensive for patient and hospital, extreme care of the instrument, longer duration of procedure are among the major reasons that have been cited for not using LA.

Keywords: laparoscopy, Open appendectomy, surgical procedures, Outcomes, cost management

Introduction: Surgical removal of the appendix is most frequent practice done in surgery. Unfortunately, most reliable procedure is still debatable. Both laparoscopic (LA) and open (OA) procedures are still in practice for surgical removal of appendix. Laparoscopic procedure is no doubt the gold standard for cholecystectomy, but laparoscopic approach is not widely used for surgical removal of appendix. Difficult handling, cost expensive for patient and hospital, extreme care of the instrument, longer duration of procedure are among the major reasons that have been cited for not using LA. With an incidence of 7-11%, acute form of appendicitis is the most frequently seen medical illness for which surgery is needed. Due to this, surgical removal of appendix is one of the most frequently performed surgeries. Laparoscopic appendectomy was first familiarized in 1983 by McBurney⁽²⁾ and Semm⁽³⁾, since then for more than hundred years OA is considered a sound and effective method for removal of appendix. Semm⁽³⁾ performed the procedure on normal appendix. While many surgeons are favoring LA in modern era, others are doubtful for replacing the safe procedure. Longer duration of operation, expensive procedure, delicate handling of the instrument and increased risk of post-op abscess makes the word “Gold Standard” debatable as used by many authors comparing OA to LA^(4, 5).

Smaller incisions, less pain post operatively, rapid discharge form hospital, quick returning to the daily activities are the advantages claimed by many proponents. In 1990’s the first broad scale series of Lap Appendectomies were published by Pier and co-workers⁽⁶⁾. It was shown that in contrast with conventional OA, LA can be done with safety and low complication rate in most of the cases of acute appendicitis. From that time multiple prospective and retrospective trials have been used to compare LA with OA. LA has been shown to be better approach than OA by some random trials but no superiority has been shown by others.⁽⁷⁾ Finding the better procedure using previous studies is main aim of this study.

Material and Methods: Peer-reviewed papers were used with the help of keywords and articles fitting the criteria were chosen and after thorough study data was established for comparing OA with LA. Medline database and data bank of PubMed was used for collecting the data. Detailed study was done on the references found.

Operative Time: Longer duration of procedure is one of the main problems associated with LA^(8, 9). This problem has been shown in multiple papers. With only a minor incision and extensive use of the procedure and surgeon’s comfortability OA is found to be better option by many surgeons. For LA extensive practice and advanced skills are needed^(9, 10). The duration of procedure in both cases are significantly different⁽¹²⁾.

Extent of Stay: Reduced time for post-op hospital stay is the commonest reason for preference of LA above OA. The shorter stay in hospital leads to decreased cost and quick come back to normal activities of daily life. In both elderly and obese patients, for the surgical removal of inflamed appendix LA is the preferred procedure. Decreased duration of stay in hospital, decreased post-op mortality and morbidity and less expenditure is associated with laparoscopic technique compared

to open technique⁽¹⁵⁾. Quick comeback to the daily life activities was associated with reduced stay in hospital as shown by Wei et al⁽¹⁶⁾. Laparoscopically operated patients had quick returning of the bowel movements, quick feeding activities and shorter stay at the hospital as compared to the patients managed with OA. The results of this study match with the previous ones showing reduced stay in hospital^(17, 18).

Complications: Increased peritoneal infections is the main drawback associated with LA^(19, 20, and 21). The procedure itself is associated with infection. Infection can be caused by simply placing the Trocar which has been shown by multiple reports⁽²²⁾. Pus formation, peritoneal abscess and long lasting ileus are usually linked with LA. The peritoneal abscess is the most lethal condition that can cause death. Lack of experience, proper skills, or perforation of the inflamed appendix are the common causes that can lead to peritoneal abscess formation^(22, 24). Routinely updated trials of Cochrane systematic review of random trials that compares OA to LA involves exploration of 39 trials⁽²⁵⁾. Three times higher ratio is found for peritoneal abscess and one and half times higher ratio of wound infection is seen after LA⁽²⁶⁾. The reason behind this higher ratio of peritoneal abscess is still unknown. Confusing results are found in the huge research going on about laparoscopic surgery and clinical association with LA is still unknown⁽²⁷⁾.

Postoperative Pain: Pain following any surgical procedure is the main headache and has to be dealt with⁽²⁸⁾. Post-op pain varies with sex and age⁽²⁹⁾, LA has reduced this issue^(30, 31). Patients treated

with open appendectomy needed stronger analgesics according to WHO pain ladder than those operated with laparoscopic procedure^(32, 33). Use of cheap painkillers put less burden on the patient.

Costs: All the papers studies showed laparoscopic technique to be expensive^(34, 35, 36). Decreased stay in hospital and cheap pain killers required decrease the cost in contrast with OA. Expenditures of open appendectomy were found to be similar in researches done by Vincenzo et al, Nakhmiyayev et al and Varela et al^(37, 38, and 39). Considering the people of different countries and age, Wei et al⁽⁴⁰⁾ found using 8 random trails that LA have cost around 11% greater than OA^(41,42). The authors still believe LA has greater expenditures as compared to OA because of greater duration of procedure and expensive instruments.

Conclusions: Laparoscopic surgery is a major breakthrough and priceless development that is a blessing for surgeons and patients. Decreased use of pain killers and reduced stay in hospitals is associated with LA. But enhanced skills, longer duration of procedure, increased peritoneal abscesses and draw backs like being an expensive procedure are also associated with LA. Other parameters like readmission cost, burden on the hospital and effects upon patient must be considered. Overall, LA is suitable for routine removal of inflamed appendix as shown by different studies. Being a safe method with enhanced effectiveness and clinically proven advantages LA can be used as gold standard approach in acute inflamed appendicitis.

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